

**GEOREFERENCED SPANISH SOIL PROFILE DATABASE
(SODES)**

METADATA

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MAIN CONTRIBUTORS

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2000 version: Bibliographic compilation of soil profiles; selection, analysis and data harmonisation, Database design. Cristina Trueba, Rocío Millán, Thomas Schmid, Carmen Lago.

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*Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas,
Medioambientales y Tecnológicas (CIEMAT)
Environmental Department
Avda. Complutense, 40
28040 Madrid (Spain)
www.ciemat.es*

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1. DATABASE OVERVIEW

The Georeferenced Spanish Soil Profile Database (SODES) contains soil information and data values for 1683 georeferenced soil profiles, compiled from an extensive bibliographic review. SODES allows the characterisation of the different peninsular Spanish soil types and is a suitable tool for assessments and decision making purposes dealing with different issues.

The origin of the soil profile Database is framed in the studies performed at the CENTRO DE INVESTIGACIONES ENERGÉTICAS, MEDIOAMBIENTALES Y TECNOLÓGICAS (CIEMAT), on the radiological vulnerability of Spanish soils to a ^{137}Cs and ^{90}Sr deposition. For this purpose, the knowledge of the different existing soil types in peninsular Spain and their adequate characterisation was needed.

This task was achieved by means of a broad compilation of soil profiles from different bibliographic sources (Trueba, et al., 2000a). The main aim was to gather profiles representative of the soil types depicted for peninsular Spain in the European Commission (EC) Soil Map at 1:1000000 scale (CEC, 1985), used as base map. The soil profile compilation was made on the province level, which is the Spanish administrative demarcation that corresponds to the NUTS-3 level (Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics) (ISO 3166-2 Standard), gathering information for the 47 peninsular provinces.

After the analysis of the information gathered and data harmonisation, a Database with 2176 soil profiles was created (Trueba, et al., 2000b), named here DB2000, allowing the characterisation of the majority of the Spanish soil types included in the EC Soil Map (CEC, 1985). The Database also contained information for other soil types that, despite actually existing in peninsular Spain, were not represented in the EC soil map.

From this large number of soil profiles, a set of 1657 were considered complete for the purposes of the radiological vulnerability assessment, and used in the methodology developed for that purpose. The results were geographically distributed (Trueba et al., 2000a) according to the Soil Typological Units (STU) and Soil Mapping Units (SMU) of the EC Soil Geographical Database, associated to the digitised EC Soil Map, using the Geographic Information System (GIS), IDRISI (Eastman, 1995).

The most up-to-date version of the EC Soil Geographical Database (EC-ESBN, 2004), which depicted more soil types for peninsular Spain than the first version, seized the opportunity to perform a new analysis of the representativeness of the 1657 complete profiles in it. This required a review of this set of profiles (Garcia-Puerta, 2014), which included the transformation of their coordinates into projected coordinates in the UTM system, according to the reference Datum ETRS-89, which is the official one for the

geographical representation in Spain (RD 1071/2007), zone 30. The validation of the newly georeferenced soil profiles (Garcia-Puerta, 2014), was made by means of the GIS, ArcMap from the ArcGIS package (ESRI, 2011).

The representativeness of the revised profiles has improved substantially, allowing the characterisation of the majority on the Spanish peninsular soil types included in the latest version of EC Soil Geographical Database. However, there are still a number of soil types in the complete dataset for which there is no representation in it and to a lesser extent, the EC Soil Geographical Database identifies some soil types for which there are no soil profiles in the dataset to associate with. These circumstances enhanced another bibliographic revision to compile new soil profiles and try to cover these gaps. Twenty-six new ones have been collated (Garcia-Puerta, 2020), allowing to improve the soil characterisation in some areas.

These new profiles, after the appropriate analysis and harmonization of their data (Garcia-Puerta, 2020), have been added to the set of revised original ones, enlarging up to 1683 the georeferenced soil profiles, which organized in a new structure, constitute the new Georeferenced Soil Profile Database (SODES), managed in Microsoft Access software. Figure 1 shows the spatial distribution of the 1683 profiles contained in the new Database and Table 1 shows the number of profiles collected at the provincial and regional levels.

Figure 1.- Soil profiles distribution in peninsular Spain. Projection UTM ETRS89-Zone30.

Table 1.- Regional (Autonomous Region-NUTS 2) and provincial (NUTS-3) surfaces. Number of complete soil profiles compiled and included in SODES at regional and provincial level. In brackets the new contributions in the provinces affected.

AUTONOMOUS REGIONS/ Provinces	Surface (10³ha)	Soil profiles included in the DB	AUTONOMOUS REGIONS/ Provinces	Surface (10³ha)	Soil profiles included in the DB
GALICIA	2951	128	ANDALUCÍA	8729	334
<i>Coruña</i>	788	38	<i>Jaén</i>	1350	49
<i>Lugo</i>	988	40	<i>Córdoba</i>	1372	52
<i>Orense</i>	727	22	<i>Sevilla</i>	1400	28
<i>Pontevedra</i>	448	28	<i>Huelva</i>	1009	40
ASTURIAS	1057	46	<i>Cádiz</i>	739	18
CANTABRIA	529	40	<i>Málaga</i>	728	24
PAÍS VASCO	727	66	<i>Granada</i>	1253	65
<i>Vizcaya</i>	222	31	<i>Almería</i>	878	58
<i>Guipúzcoa</i>	200	16	CASTILLA-LEÓN	9415	312
<i>Álava</i>	305	19	<i>León</i>	1547	32
EXTREMADURA	4161	84	<i>Zamora</i>	1056	29
<i>Cáceres</i>	1995	40	<i>Salamanca</i>	1234	50
<i>Badajoz</i>	2166	44	<i>Palencia</i>	803	18
VALENCIA	2330	84	<i>Valladolid</i>	820	57
<i>Alicante</i>	586	12	<i>Ávila</i>	805	40
<i>Valencia</i>	1076	52	<i>Burgos</i>	1427	32 (1)
<i>Castellón</i>	668	20	<i>Soria</i>	1029	30
MURCIA	1312	32	<i>Segovia</i>	694	23
MADRID	799	54	CATALUÑA	3191	99
CASTILLA-LA MANCHA	7923	191	<i>Barcelona</i>	773	27
<i>Toledo</i>	1537	32	<i>Tarragona</i>	628	21
<i>Ciudad Real</i>	1975	47 (1)	<i>Lérida</i>	1203	26
<i>Guadalajara</i>	1219	42	<i>Girona</i>	587	25
<i>Cuenca</i>	1706	36 (1)	ARAGÓN	4766	117
<i>Albacete</i>	1486	31 (1)	<i>Huesca</i>	1567	46 (18)
NAVARRA	1042	66	<i>Zaragoza</i>	1719	19 (4)
LA RIOJA	503	30	<i>Teruel</i>	1480	30

2. SOIL PROFILE INFORMATION

The soil profile information collated from the bibliographic compilation is summarized in Table 2. It contains, in addition to the morphological descriptions and analytical soil parameters, a general information section related to the soil profile's:

- Location, referring to the province, municipality and specific situation within it. In case some of this information is not given, but the bibliographic source refers to a certain place (such as roads, lanes, buildings, or others), it is also included in the descriptive sheet. Other data as altitude, expressed in meters above sea level, and slope, expressed in percentage, is also included,

- Coordinates, geographic or UTM as well as the sheet number of the National Topographic Map (MTN) at 1:50.000 scale in which the soil profile is located,
- Land use,
- Number of horizons for which the information is available,
- Soil type classification.

The bibliographic source from which the profile data was obtained, is also included in the soil sheet as well as the identification code given to the profile by the author. Other type of available information in the source that could be useful for soil description purposes, such as the type of parent material, the type of dominant clay, the existence of phreatic layers, gypsum, etc., is also included in the soil profile's comments section.

Table 2.- Soil profile information collated.

SOIL PROFILE CODE:		MTN-Sheet ¹ :
Province:	Municipality:	UTM, zone 30
Situation:		X: Y
Land Use		Longitude:(W/E) ° ' "
Slope:		Latitude: ° ' "
Reference:		Altitude (m):
SOIL CLASSIFICATION		Author's profile code:
FAO Legend (1974):		Nº Horizons:
USDA – Soil taxonomy (1975):		
Horizon number:	Colour:	Boundary:
Name:	Texture:	Structure:
Depth (cm):	Consistence:	Roots:
	Infiltration (mm h ⁻¹):	Bulk density (g cm ⁻³):
	pH (H ₂ O):	EC (mScm ⁻¹):
	CaCO ₃ (%):	Coarse elements (%):
	C/N:	<i>Exchangeable cations (cmol kg⁻¹)</i>
	OM (%):	Ca:
	<i>Particle size distribution (USDA)</i>	Mg:
	Coarse Sand (%):	Na:
	Fine Sand (%):	K:
	Silt (%):	S:
	Clay (%):	CEC (cmol kg ⁻¹):
COMMENTS:		V (%):

As for the morphological description and specific physical and chemical properties of each soil profile, the information, given at horizon level, includes the following data, as shown in Table 2:

¹ National Topographic Map Sheet

- Morphological data: referred to the thickness of each horizon, expressed in cm; the boundary, colour, texture, structure, consistence and root development descriptions.
- Analytical data: referred to the measured values of the pH (measured in water), the electrical conductivity (EC) of the saturation extract in mS cm⁻¹, the infiltration capacity of water expressed in mm h⁻¹, the percentage of calcium carbonate, the percentage of organic matter content, the bulk density expressed in g cm⁻³, the carbon to nitrogen ratio, the percentage of coarse elements, the particle size distribution, as well as the data referring to the exchange complex that includes the exchangeable cations (Ca, Mg, Na and K) content expressed in cmol kg⁻¹, the sum of bases (S) and the cation exchange capacity (CEC), expressed both, also in cmol kg⁻¹ as well as the percentage of base saturation (V).

For identification purposes, each profile collected was assigned a Soil Profile Code, an alphanumeric value combining the acronym of the name of the province where it belonged and a two digit number, following the sequential order in which it was compiled.

The wide variety of bibliographic sources consulted provided a certain degree of heterogeneity in the type of information collated, which made necessary an analysis of the data compiled, to harmonise, as much as possible, the information contained in the Database. Annex 2 summarizes this process.

3. GEORREFERENCING, NEW CONTRIBUTIONS AND UPDATED DATABASE DESIGN

The latest version of the European Soil Database (EC-ESBN, 2004), which depicted more soil types for peninsular Spain than the first version, seized the opportunity to make a new analysis of the representativeness of the 1657 complete soil profiles in it.

This, required a revision of them, process that included the transformation of all the coordinates into projected coordinates in the UTM system (Garcia-Puerta, 2014), according to the reference Datum ETRS-89, which is the official one for geographical representations in Spain (RD 1071/2007), zone 30.

Regarding the coordinate system, several situations were encountered. For those profiles for which their geographic or UTM coordinates were available, it was assumed that in both cases, they referred to the ED-50 Datum, and were transformed to refer to the UTM system, reference Datum ETRS-89. For those soil profiles which had no coordinate information, other geographical references were used to locate them, such as the municipality and/or its situation within it. The sheets of the National Topographic Map and other available maps at higher resolution scales were used to geographically locate them and their UTM coordinates were assigned, taking the ETRS-89 Datum as a reference. All of them were georeferenced using the GIS, ArcMap, (ESRI, 2011) and the new coordinates verified.

The representativeness of the 1657 newly georeferenced soil profiles in the European Soil Database (EC-ESBN, 2004), has improved substantially, allowing the characterization of the majority of the Spanish peninsular soil types included in it. However, there are still some profiles for which there is no representation, and to a lesser extent, the European Soil Database identifies some types of soil for which there are no soil profiles in the dataset to associate with. This has led to a new bibliographic review to collect new profiles and try to fill these gaps. This revision also tried to increase the density of profiles per hectare in areas where it was very low or non-existent. Twenty-six new ones have been collated (Garcia-Puerta, 2020), allowing to improve the characterisation in some areas.

The new soil profiles have undergone the same data analysis and harmonisation process, that the former ones, being the only exception the soil classification which has been done in the frame of a Doctoral Thesis (Garcia-Puerta, 2020), where no 1975 USDA Soil Taxonomy classification has been considered.

These new profiles have been added to the newly georeferenced and revised complete ones, constituting the Georeferenced Soil Database of Spanish Soils (SODES) with 1683 soil profiles. To distinguish the new contributions from the original ones, the Soil Profile Code notation has changed, introducing a three-digit number (instead of two), jointly with the province name acronym; in such a way that the new ones start in 101. The allocation of the soil profiles at regional and province levels (NUTS-2 and NUTS-3, respectively), was seen in Table 1.

The soil information is organised in an updated structure and managed in Microsoft Access software. The data are stored in different tables that include for each soil profile, their general description and location data, the values of the specific physical and chemical properties, given at horizon level, the citations of the bibliographic sources from which the information was compiled, the codes used to facilitate the traceability of the harmonisation done, the codes used to interpret the descriptive parameters and the complete province names. The new structure of the Database, the tables that store the data and their dependence is shown below.

4. UPDATED DATABASE DESIGN. TABLES: DESCRIPTIONS AND ACCESS DATA MODEL

4.1 TABLE DESCRIPTIONS

All the information on the soil profiles has been compiled from Spanish bibliographic references and they have been incorporated into the Database in this language. To facilitate its dissemination, its structure has been arranged in English, translating the column headings of all the tables containing the data. Regarding these, the numerical values of the analytical properties have not required translation. As for the information

on location, land use and profile remarks, due to the extensive and varied information collected, which makes their translation very complex, they have been kept in the original language. The nomenclature of the FAO classification and the descriptions of the codes used, both in the descriptive soil properties and the harmonization process have also been translated.

The soil information is structured in the following tables:

- DB2020_1683_PROFILES: contains the generic information of the soil profiles.
- HORIZON DATA: contains for each horizon, the morphological and analytical data.
- REFERENCE: contains, for each profile, the codes assigned to identify the bibliographic source from which the information was obtained.
- REFERENCE_SOURCE: contains the full citation of the reference.
- HARMONI: contains the harmonisation codes assigned to each soil profile, when needed.
- HARMONI_DESCRIP: identifies the harmonisation work carried out.
- FAO74_LEGEND: contains the names and codes of the 1974 FAO Legend.
- PROV_CODE: contains the province code and the corresponding province name according to the ISO 3166-2_ES Standard.
- M_COLOUR: contains the codes assigned to describe the soil colour.
- M_BOUNDARY: contains the codes assigned to describe the soil boundary.
- M_TEXTURE: contains the codes assigned to describe the soil texture.
- M_STRUCTURE: contains the codes assigned to describe the soil structure.
- M_CONSIST: contains the codes assigned to describe the soil consistence.
- M_ROOTS: contains the codes assigned to describe root development.

The description of the contents of the different tables is described as follows.

The **DB2020_1683 PROFILES Table**, has the following data,

- DB_PROF_ID_NB: Database Profile Identification Number. It is the profile sequential number within the entire Database. It is first attributed to the original profiles, sorted alphabetically according to the PROF_CODE, and then to the new ones, equally sorted.
- PROF_CODE: Profile Code, is the profile identifier within the province, an alphanumeric value that combines the acronym name of the province where it belongs (PROV_CODE), and a three-digit number that follows the sequential order in which it was compiled (PROF_PROV_NB).
- PROV_CODE: Province name. Refers to the Spanish province identifier acronym according to the ISO 3166-2 Standard.
- PROF_PROV_NB: Sequential number of the profile, within the province, assigned during the compilation process.

- X_UTM_ETRS: X coordinate in UTM System, according to the European Terrestrial Reference 1989 Datum, Zone 30.
- Y_UTM_ETRS: Y coordinate in UTM System, according to the European Terrestrial Reference 1989 Datum, Zone 30.
- MTN_SHEET: Spanish National Topographic Map Sheet.
- MUN_NAME: Municipality name where the profile is situated.
- LOCATION: Location name or specific situation such as roads, lanes, buildings or others.
- LANDUSE: Land use description.
- SLOPE: Slope in %.
- ALTITUDE: Altitude in meters above sea level.
- REFERENCE: Bibliographic reference from which the soil profile information has been collated.
- PROF_ID_NB_REF: Profile identification number within the reference. Refers to the number given to the profile by the author.
- NB_OF_HORIZON: Number of horizons in the soil profile.
- FAO74_NAME_ES: 1974 FAO legend soil name, in Spanish.
- FAO74_CODE: 1974 FAO legend soil code.
- PROF_COMMENTS: Author's soil classification and other type of available information in the source and that could be useful for the soil description, such as the type of parent material, the type of dominant clay, the existence of phreatic layers, gypsum, etc. The extensive information gathered, has not allowed a proper translation into English, but Table 3, shows the correspondences of the most frequent remarks.
- USDA75_NAME: 1975 USDA Soil Taxonomy name.
- USDA75_ORDER: 1975 USDA Order name.
- USDA75_SUBORDER: 1975 USDA Suborder name.
- USDA75_GGROUP: 1975 USDA Great group name.

Table 3 .- Spanish-English correspondences of the most frequent comments.

SPANISH	ENGLISH
MATERIAL ORIGINARIO	PARENT MATERIAL
CLASIFICACION AUTOR	AUTHOR CLASSIFICATION
SUELO SOBRE MATERIAL CUATERNARIO	FLOOR ON QUATERNARY MATERIAL
LOS DATOS DE CATIONES VIENEN DADOS	THE CATION DATA ARE GIVEN
EN (mg/100 g)	IN (mg / 100 g)
SUELO SOBRE	SOIL ON
CAPA FREATICA	WATER TABLE

The **HORIZON DATA Table**, has the following data,

- HOR_ID_NB: Database Horizon Identification Number. It is the horizon sequential number within the total Database, sorted according to the profile code (PROF_CODE).
- HOR_CODE: Horizon Code. It is the horizon identifier within the profile, an alphanumeric value formed with the province identifier acronym (PROV_CODE) and a five-digit number which contains the profile code (PROF_CODE) and the number sequentially assigned to the horizon along the profile (HOR_ORDER_NB).
- PROF_CODE: Profile Code, is the profile identifier within the province, an alphanumeric value that combines the acronym name of the province where it belongs (PROV_CODE), and a three-digit number that follows the sequential order in which it was compiled (PROF_PROV_NB).
- HOR_ORDER_NB: Sequential order of the horizon within the soil profile.
- HOR_NAME: Horizon name.
- M_DEPTH_UPP: Horizon depth in cm; the first horizon is measured from the surface of the soil downwards, the following ones from the upper boundary of each of them.
- M_THICKNESS: Thickness of the soil horizon in cm.
- M_BOUNDARY: Horizon boundary description follows the codes given in Annex 1.
- M_COLOUR: Soil colour description, follows the codes given in Annex 1.
- M_TEXTURE: USDA textural class; Annex 1 shows the codes used to define them.
- M_STRUCT: Soil structure; Annex 1 shows the codes used to define the soil units or aggregates.
- M_CONSIST: Soil consistency, describes the degree and kind of cohesion/adhesion of soil particles; follows the codes used in Annex 1.
- M_ROOTS: Root development description; follows the codes given in Annex 1.
- M_INFILT: infiltration value given in mm h^{-1} .
- A_PH: pH value measured in water.
- A_EC: Electrical conductivity value of the saturation extract given in mS cm^{-1} .
- A_CACO3: % of calcium carbonate.
- A_BDENSITY: Bulk density value given in g cm^{-3} .
- A_COARSEEL: % of coarse elements, soil particles with a size greater than 2,0 mm.
- A_COARSE_SAND: % of coarse sand fraction.
- A_FINE_SAND: % of fine sand fraction.
- A_SAND_TOT: % of total sand fraction.
- A_SILT: % of silt fraction.
- A_CLAY: % of clay fraction.
- A_C/N: Carbon to nitrogen ratio.

- A_OM: % of organic matter content.
- A_EXCH_CA: Exchangeable Ca content value, in cmol kg^{-1} .
- A_EXCH_MG: Exchangeable Mg content value, in cmol kg^{-1} .
- A_EXCH_NA: Exchangeable Na content value, in cmol kg^{-1} .
- A_EXCH_K: Exchangeable K content value, in cmol kg^{-1} .
- A_SUM_BASES_S: Total sum of bases value, in cmol kg^{-1} .
- A_CEC: Cation exchange capacity value, in cmol kg^{-1} .
- A_BASE_SAT_V: Base saturation given as the % of the CEC taken by the total sum of bases.
- HOR_COMMENTS: Contains comments referred to the horizons.

The **REFERENCE Table**, has the following data,

- PROF_CODE: Profile Code, is the profile identifier within the province, an alphanumeric value that combines the acronym name of the province where it belongs (PROV_CODE), and a three-digit number that follows the sequential order in which it was compiled (PROF_PROV_NB).
- REF_CODE: Reference code of the bibliographic reference.

The **REFERENCE_SOURCE Table**, has the following data,

- REF_CODE: Reference code of the bibliographic source.
- REF_SOURCE_TXT: Full reference citation.

The **HARMONI Table**, has the following data,

- PROF_CODE: Profile Code, is the profile identifier within the province, an alphanumeric value that combines the acronym name of the province where it belongs (PROV_CODE), and a three-digit number that follows the sequential order in which it was compiled (PROF_PROV_NB).
- HARMONI_CODES: Codes used to identify the data harmonised or estimated.

The **HARMONI DESCRIP Table**, has the following data,

- HARMONI_CODES: Codes used to identify the data harmonised or estimated.
- HARMONI_DESCRIPTION: Description of the harmonisation and estimation codes (HARMONI_CODES), as shown in Table 4. The detailed descriptions for each code are collected in Annex 1.

Table 4.- Description of the harmonization codes

CODES	DESCRIPTION
A	HORIZON DENOMINATION STANDARISED
B	BULK DENSITY VALUE ESTIMATED
C	EXCHANGEABLE Ca CONTENT REVISED
D	EXCHANGEABLE CEC CONTENT ESTIMATED
E	EXCHANGEABLE V CONTENT ESTIMATED
F	EXCHANGEABLE S CONTENT ESTIMATED
G	EXCHANGEABLE C/N CONTENT ESTIMATED
H	EXCHANGEABLE OM CONTENT ESTIMATED
I	TEXTURE STANDARISED
J	TEXTURE DETERMINED
K	SALINE SOIL
L	SOIL PARTICLE DISTRIBUTION REVISED
M	pH VALUE ESTIMATED

The **FAO74 LEGEND Table**, has the following data,

- FAO74_CODE: 1974 FAO Legend soil code.
- FAO74_NAME_ES: 1974 FAO Legend soil name in Spanish.
- FAO74_NAME_EN: 1974 FAO Legend soil name in English.

The **PROV_CODE Table**, has the following data,

- PROV_CODE: Province name. Refers to the Spanish province identifier acronym according to the ISO 3166-2 Standard.
- ISO 3166-2_ES: Standard used to identify the province.
- PROV_NAME: Full written province name.

The **Table M_COLOUR**, has the following information,

- M_COLOUR: Codes used to identify the colour description (Annex 1).
- Colour descrip_EN: English description.
- Colour descrip_ES: Spanish description.

The **Table M_BOUNDARY**, has the following information,

- M_BOUNDARY: Codes used to identify the horizon boundary description (Annex 1).
- Boundary descrip_EN: English description.
- Boundary descrip_ES: Spanish description.

The **Table M_TEXTURE**, has the following information,

- M_TEXTURE: Codes used to identify the soil texture description (Annex 1).
- Texture descrip_EN: English description.
- Texture descrip_ES: Spanish description.

The **Table M_STRUCTURE**, has the following information,

- M_STRUCTURE: Codes used to identify the soil structure description (Annex 1).
- Structure descrip_EN: English description.
- Structure descrip_ES: Spanish description.

The **Table M_CONSIST**, has the following information,

- M_CONSIST: Codes used to identify the soil consistence description (Annex 1).
- Consist descrip_EN: English description.
- Consist descrip_ES: Spanish description.

The **Table M_ROOTS**, has the following information,

- M_ROOTS: Codes used to identify the root development description (Annex 1).
- Roots descrip_EN: English description.
- Roots descrip_ES: Spanish description.

4.2 ACCESS DATA MODEL

The dependences established among the different described tables are shown in Figure 2. From the identifier code of each of the soil profiles (PROF_CODE), which correspond to the main key of the DB2020_1683_PROFILES, HORIZON DATA, REFERENCE and HARMONI tables, a relation between the first of them and each of the following tables has been established.

In turn, the REFERENCES table is related, through the REF_CODE field, to the table that contains the complete reference of the source from which the soil information was extracted, the REFERENCE SOURCE table.

In addition, the HARMONI table, in which the harmonised parameters are indicated to make a homogenized Database, is related to the HARMONI DESCRIP table, where each of the possible actions carried out for such harmonization are described; this dependence has been made through the HARMONI_CODES field.

Additionally, the relation between the DB2020_1683_PROFILES and PROV_CODE tables is included, through the identifier code of the province of each profile (PROV_CODE) and

between the first table and the FAO74 LEGEND table, through the FAO74_CODE field, which identifies the profile's soil classification according to FAO-UNESCO (1974).

The classes' codification and description in English and Spanish, of the following soil parameters have been included in the Access Database: colour (M_COLOUR), horizon boundary (M_BOUNDARY), texture (M_TEXTURE), structure (M_STRUCTURE), roots (M_ROOTS) and consistence (M_CONSIST). The dependence between each parameter's table and the one which includes the horizons' data (HORIZON DATA) results in a non-referential integrity, since the horizons may be characterised with more than one parameter's class.

Figure 2.- Tables dependences (Access data model)

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ANNEX 1
HARMONISATION PROCESS

As explained before, the wide variety of bibliographic sources consulted (technical works, scientific journals, doctoral thesis, soil maps, dissertations, field guides or conference books), published in an extended period of time, provided a certain degree of heterogeneity in the type of information collated. This, specifically affected the soil classifications, the coordinate system, some units and the description of some parameters, and made necessary an analysis of the data compiled to harmonise, as much as possible, the information contained in the Database.

Heterogeneity was also encountered in the level of the information given. Usually, the sources had parameter values for all the horizons described, although not necessarily for all the parameters requested in Table 2. Occasionally, some sources only gave values for some horizons; on other occasions, values were given only for some parameters but allowed, whenever possible and necessary, to derive some missing values from them.

The harmonisation process includes the adaptation of the soil information, according to the standards selected and the derivation of some parameters, when necessary and possible. It is important to highlight that for some data, mostly soil descriptions, this has been possible with some limitations, keeping in the Database the codes given in the bibliographic source.

In order to keep the traceability of the harmonisation done, a soil profile control sheet with the codes assigned in each case, was prepared to compliment the soil profile descriptive sheet (Trueba, et al., 1998a)-(Trueba, et al., 1999j). This codification did not affect the soil type classification as all the profiles have been reclassified according to the selected standards, the 1974 FAO-UNESCO Legend (FAO, 1974) and the 1975 United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) Soil Taxonomy (USDA, 1975), but keeping the original soil classification given by the author in the profile's comments record

Regarding the coordinate system, the DB2000 version kept the information given by the author in each soil profile.

Soil horizon designations

The horizon denominations have been standardised following the FAO (Carballas, et al., 1981; FAO, 1998).

Boundary description, colour, consistence and root development

For each horizon, the depth of the upper and lower boundaries are given in centimetres, measured from the surface of the soil, downwards. The description of these boundaries was made in terms of distinctness and/or topography. Table 1.1 shows the codes, in English and Spanish, used to describe the boundary description (Roquero and Porta, 1995).

Table 1.1.- Codes used to describe the boundary of the soil horizons (Roquero and Porta, 1995).

BOUNDARY DESCRIPTION		DESCRIPCIÓN DE LÍMITES	
Distinctness codes	MA-Very abrupt (<0,5cm) A/B-Abrupt (<2cm) N-Clear (2-5cm) G-Gradual (5-12 cm) D-Diffuse (>12 cm)	Distinción:	MA-Muy abrupto (<0,5cm) A/B-Abrupto (<2cm) N-Neto (2-5cm) G-Gradual (5-12 cm) D-Difuso (>12 cm)
Topography codes	S-Smooth P-Plane O-Wavy IR-Irregular IN-Inclined B-Broken	Topografía:	S-Suave P-Plano O-Ondulado IR-Irregular IN-Inclinado B-Roto

Regarding the soil colour, whenever the bibliographic source gave it, the Munsell soil colour (Porta, et al., 1999), was taken. In other cases, the horizon was described by means of a generic dominant colour or as mottled with two or more colours. Table 1.2 shows, in English and Spanish, the standard Munsell colour names (the five principal hues) and a generic colour codes used in those cases where the Munsell colour was not given, derived from the indicative colours of the oxidation-reduction state of the horizon (Porta, et al., 1999).

Table 1.2.- Codes used to describe the colour of the soil horizons (Porta, et al., 1999).

COLOUR		COLOR	
Munsell Soil Colour Chart:	R-Red Y-Yellow G-Green B-Blue P-Purple	Tabla de color Munsell:	R-Rojo Y-Amarillo G-Verde B-Azúl P-Violeta
Generic colour code. Dominant colour:	P-Brown R-Redish A-Yellowish G-Grey O-Ochre V-Violet B-White N-Black	Código del color genérico dominante:	P-Pardo R-Rojizo A-Amarillento G-Gris O-Ocre V-Violeta B-Blanquecino N-Negro
Lightness:	o-dark c-pale	Brillo:	o-oscuro c-claro

In relation to the soil consistence and the root development, the codes, in English and Spanish, used to facilitate their descriptions (Roquero and Porta, 1995), are included, respectively, in Tables 1.3 and 1.4. The consistence refers to the degree and kind of cohesion and adhesion with which the soil particles are held together and varies with moisture content; while the root development refers to the size and/or quantity of the roots present in the horizon.

Table 1.3.- Codes used to describe the soil consistence (Roquero and Porta, 1995).

SOIL CONSISTENCE			CONSISTENCIA		
DRY	MOIST	WET	SECO	HUMEDO	MOJADO
S-Loose B-Soft LD-Slightly hard D-Hard MD-Very hard ED-Extremely hard	S-Loose MFR-Very friable FR-Friable F-Firm MF-Very firm EF-Extremely firm	NP-Non plastic LP-Slightly plastic P-Moderately plastic MP-Very plastic NA-Non sticky LA-Slightly sticky A-Moderately sticky MA-Very sticky	S-Suelto B-Blando LD-Ligeramente duro D-Duro MD-Muy duro ED-Extremadamente duro	S-Suelto MFR-Muy friable FR-Friable F-Firme MF-Muy firme EF-Extremadamente firme	NP-No plastico LP-Ligeramente plastico P-Moderadamente plastico MP-Muy plastico NA-No adherente LA-Ligeramente adherente A-Adherente MA-Muy adherente

Table 1.4.- Codes used to describe the root development (Roquero and Porta, 1995).

ROOT DEVELOPMENT	DESARROLLO RADICULAR
QUANTITY	CANTIDAD
MA-Very abundant A-Abundant MF-Very frequent F-Frequent P-Few MP-Very few N-None	MA-Muy abundante A-Abundante MF-Muy frecuente F-Frecuente P-Pocas MP-Muy pocas N-Ninguna
SIZE	TAMAÑO
f-Thin (<2mm) M-Medium (2-5mm) G-Thick (>5mm)	f-Finas (<2mm) M-Medias (2-5mm) G-Gruesas (>5mm)

Depending on the bibliographic source of the soil profile, some of these properties are not described, and therefore, not included in the Database. In other cases, the codes used to describe them do not follow the standard selected and this occurs specifically in the case of the boundaries description, and to a lesser extent to the other descriptions. The codes given by the author have been kept in the Database.

Distribution of soil particles

The size distribution of soil particles followed (USDA, 1987) considers the following separates:

- Sand: 2.0 - 0.05 mm
- Silt: 0.05 - 0.002 mm
- Clay: < 0.002 mm

Being the sand separate subdivided in:

- Coarse sand: 2.0 - 0.5 mm
- Fine sand: 0.5 - 0.05 mm

The relative percentages of sand, silt, and clay given for each horizon were revised, so that the total sum of the fractions reached 100%, assuming an error range of $\pm 5\%$. When the value obtained did not reach or exceeded such range, in any of the horizons, that profile was discarded as complete. Occasionally, the information given included the fraction of coarse elements jointly with the relative percentages of sand, silt, and clay. In this case, this fraction was removed and the rest normalised adjusting to 100%.

Soil texture

The percentage of the different soil separates, in each horizon, define the soil texture. The USDA soil textural classes (USDA, 1987), were used to harmonise or estimate, when necessary and possible, the horizon texture. Table 1.5, shows the codes used to define the soil textural classes.

Table 1.5.- Codes used to define the soil USDA textural classes (USDA, 1987).

SOIL TEXTURE	TEXTURA DEL SUELO
A-SAND	A-ARENOSA
FA-LOAMY SAND	FA- FRANCO ARENOSA
AF-SANDY LOAM	AF- ARENOSA FRANCA
F-LOAM	F-FRANCA
FL-SILTY LOAM	FL- FRANCO LIMOSA
L-SILT	L-LIMOSA
FCA-SANDY CLAY LOAM	FCA- FRANCO ARCILLO ARENOSA
FC-CLAY LOAM	FC- FRANCO ARCILLOSA
FCL-SILTY CLAY LOAM	FCL- FRANCO ARCILLO LIMOSA
CA-SANDY CLAY	CA- ARCILLO ARENOSA
CL-SILTY CLAY	CL- ARCILLO LIMOSA
C-CLAY	C-ARCILLOSA

Soil structure

Soil structure refers to the natural organization of soil particles into discrete soil units or aggregates. These aggregates vary in size and shape, being the codes, in English and Spanish, used to describe the structure, in each horizon, shown in Table 1.6 (Porta, et al., 1999).

Table 1.6.- Codes used to describe the structure description (Porta, et al., 1999).

STRUCTURE CODES	
GS- GRANULAR	GS- GRANULAR SIMPLE
G- CRUMBLY	G- MIGAJOSA
L- PLATY	L- LAMINAR
P- PRISMATIC	P- PRISMÁTICA
C-COLUMNAR	C- COLUMNAR
B- BLOCKY	B- BLOQUES
M- ROCK STRUCTURE	M- ESTRUCTURA FUERTE
N- MASSIVE	N- SIN ESTRUCTURA

Harmonisation of names and units of the exchange complex

Most of the data collated from the bibliographic sources, expressed the cation content as *exchange or exchangeable cation*, in cmol kg^{-1} . This was the standard to follow in those cases where the information collected was not given this way. Several situations were encountered,

- When the cation content was referred to as *nutrient reservoir*, it was assumed that it meant exchangeable cation.
- When the cation content was referred to as *extractable cation*, it was assumed as the sum of the exchangeable and soluble cations. Given the case, acidic pH values and electrical conductivity (EC) values lesser than 0.5 mS cm^{-1} , would indicate that there were no soluble cations, assuming then, that the extractable cation was exchangeable.
- The analysis of the pH and EC values was also applied when the cation data was given in ppm without any other reference. Again, for acidic pH and EC values lesser than 0.5 mS cm^{-1} , it was assumed that the cation was exchangeable and the data transformed to cmol kg^{-1} .
- When the cation content was directly referred to as *soluble cation*, or the units of the cation value were given in mEq l^{-1} , ppm, $\text{mEq } 100\text{gr}^{-1}$ or the information given was referred to data obtained from the saturated extract or saturated soil paste extract, it was assumed that the information given belonged to soluble cations and the soil profile was discarded as complete.

Normalization of the exchangeable Ca value

In some soil profiles, specifically in those where the limestone content was high, the value given for the sum of bases was greater than the one given for the CEC. In these cases, it was assumed that the Ca data supplied included both, the exchangeable and the soluble fraction of the cation. The normalization done equals the sum of bases value to the CEC one, being the exchangeable Ca value obtained by subtracting the content of Mg, Na and K from the sum of bases.

Estimation of the cation exchange capacity (CEC) value

The CEC value was mostly collated in the soil profile compilation. In those cases in which the values were not given, they were derived from the following relationship, provided that the other parameters S and V, had given values:

$$CEC = [\text{sum of the base cations (S)}/\text{base saturation (V)}] \times 100$$

Estimation of the sum of bases (S)

This information was usually given in the profile information. In those cases in which it was not given, it was estimated from the sum of the exchangeable cation contents.

Estimation of the percentage of base saturation (V)

As the previous parameter, the base saturation (V) was mostly collated in the profile compilation. When it was not given and provided that the values from the other parameters were available, it was derived using the previous equation, expressed as a percentage. Occasionally this value was also estimated from the pH value, according to the relationship shown in Table 1.7 (Roquero and Porta, 1995), used to determine, quantitatively, among other parameters, the soil potential productivity.

Table 1.7- Relationship between pH and the base saturation (Roquero and Porta, 1995).

pH	PERCENTAGE OF BASE SATURATION (V%)
≤ 4	≤ 10
4 – 5	10 – 35
5 – 6	35 – 60
6 – 7	60 – 75
> 7	> 75

Estimation of the pH value

The value of pH was given in mostly all of the soil profiles compiled. In the cases in which it was not available it was estimated from the correlation between pH and the base saturation shown in Table 1.7.

Estimation of the bulk density value

When the value of this data was not given in the soil profile information, it was derived from the values given for the texture (Porta, et al., 1999), as shown in Table 1.8.

Table 1.8 .- Bulk density values estimation based on the soil texture.

TEXTURE	BULK DENSITY (g cm⁻³)
SANDY (A, FA)	1,68
LOAM SANDY (AF)	1,52
LOAM (F,FL, L)	1,36
LOAM CLAYEY (FC, FCA, FCL)	1,21
CLAYEY (C, CA, CL)	1,16

Estimation of the organic matter percentage

This value was generally given as such in almost all soil profiles. When the data provided was organic carbon, the soil organic matter percentage was estimated multiplying the percentage of organic carbon by a factor of 1,724 (Van Bemmelen factor), based on the assumption that organic matter contains 58% of organic carbon (Porta, et al., 1999).